

Ireland

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Ireland, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

Ireland's higher education system is a binary system with Universities and Institutes of Technology¹. The Higher Education Authority was established in 1968 as a key intermediary agency between the state and the universities with important planning and budgetary responsibilities for the university sector. In 1971 the National Council for Educational Awards was set up with academic responsibilities for the non-university sector. Today, the Irish higher education system comprises four types of HEIs:

- Universities
- Institutes of Technology
- Technological Universities
- Specialist Colleges

There are seven **public Universities** in Ireland: The National University of Ireland has four constituent Universities at Dublin, Cork, Galway and Maynooth which are largely independent under the Universities Act of 1997. The University of Dublin with its single college, Trinity College, is the oldest university (established in 1592). The other two universities are the University of Limerick and Dublin City University.

During the 1960s, Ireland built up a binary higher education system introducing the **Institutes of Technology (IoT)**. Since that time the IoT sector has grown and is regarded as being highly successful. Until 2018, there were 14 Institutes of Technology located throughout the country, located in Dublin, Athlone, Carlow, Cork, Dundalk, Galway-Mayo, Letterkenny, Limerick, Sligo, Tallaght, Tralee, Waterford, Blanchardstown and Dun Laoghaire. Most of these Institutes evolved from Regional Technical Colleges, having been awarded their new titles in 1998. The institutes provide a comprehensive range of courses including craft and apprentice programmes, higher technical and technological education through two-year Higher Certificate, three-year Ordinary Bachelor Degree, and four-year Honours Bachelor Degrees. The institutes also provide a range of postgraduate programmes at Postgraduate Diploma, Master's, and Doctoral level. The programmes of study offered in some institutions may include a period of work outside the institution as part of the course of study.

¹Note that Eurydice does not list Technological Universities as separate category.

<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/ireland/types-higher-education-institutions-0>

The institutes also play an important role in providing for recurrent educational needs by way of part-time and evening courses, as well as catering for continuing professional education. Details of all courses in Higher Education appear in the EU Student Handbook.

Following a new enactment of legislation in 2018, Institutes of Technology began a merger process with the aim to create five **Technological Universities** in Ireland, two of which have already been established in 2019 and 2020/21. Technological Universities address the social and economic needs of their region, they engage in industry-focused research and are vocationally and professionally oriented. No formal distinctions exist regarding qualifications from the non-university and the university sectors.

Specialist Colleges include Colleges of Education and Recognised Colleges of the National University of Ireland. The Colleges of Education are privately owned and are devoted predominantly to teacher education of primary and post-primary levels, whereby in recent years, some of the colleges offer general degrees and postgraduate studies. Both, the Colleges of Education and the Recognised Colleges are closely linked to universities in terms of their academic and quality assurance procedures. They benefit from state support (recurrent grant and undergraduate free fees), and their academic awards are made by the relevant university.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics for the four public Irish HEI types. In total there are 22 public HEIs established in Ireland. Ireland also has a number of independent private providers of higher education. The seven Universities and the Technological Universities are all PhD awarding, as is the case for the majority of the Colleges and the Institutes of Technology with only one in each of the categories being non-PhD awarding.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category	N	Public	PhD awarding
College	4	4	3
Institute of Technology	9	9	8
Technological University	2	2	2
University	7	7	7
Total	22	22	20

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Figure 1 shows the emergence of the current Irish higher education system over time. Universities and Colleges have rather deep historical roots, with the University of Dublin and its only College, the Trinity College, being the oldest established University (1592). Three further universities as well as one college were founded before the second World War. One University was established in the 1970s, one in the 1980s and the last one in 1997 (Maynooth University). Institutes of Technology were established in Ireland in the 1960s, with their number increasing steeply between 1964 (establishment of the Institute of Technology, Carlow as the first one) and 1979 (Dún Laoghaire Institute of Art, Design and Technology as the last).

The Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin) was formally established on January 1, 2019, resulting from a merger of three Institutes of Technology in the Dublin area. Munster Technological University (MTU) started operations in January 2021 as the result of a merger between two Institutes of Technology in Cork and Tralee. MTU is a public Technological University consisting of six campuses located in County Cork and County Kerry. These mergers brought the number of IoTs in Ireland from 14 in 2018 down to 9 in 2021.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Mind that Figure 1 only displays organisations that were independent at the end of the reported period, so that the figure does not account for mergers or other demographic events. For instance, five Institutes of

Technology have been merged into two new Technological Universities in the last two reporting years, reducing the number of Institutes of Technology from 14 (according to 2018 data) to 9 to (actual data).

Students

Figure 2 provides an overview of the numbers of students enrolled, disaggregated by ISCED level across the main institution types. Universities account for about 54% of total students and are attended by the vast majority of PhD students (83%). Institutes of Technology, the largest group in terms of the number of institutions, account for about a quarter of total students, which are mostly Bachelor students. The number of Master and PhD students enrolled in IoTs is much lower. The four colleges – about 18% of total institutions in terms of establishments – account for only 5% of all students in Irish HEIs, though quite equally distributed across ISCED levels. The two new Technological Universities (TU Dublin and MTU) account for a remarkably high share of students in Irish HEIs (17%).

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students includes ISCED 5-7

Financial resources

Figure 3 underlines the results from the previous section, showing that in 2020 Universities accounted not only for the majority of students enrolled (54%), but with 67% also for the largest share of total revenues among all HEIs. This may be related to the fact that Universities play a much stronger role in the acquisition of third-party funds and student fees. In contrast, Institutes of Technology show a comparably lower share of total revenues

(17%) when compared to the share of the number of students enrolled (24%). Similarly, the Technological Universities receive a decent share of total revenues (14%) while their share of enrolled students is 17%. Colleges have the lowest share in total revenues (2.4%), also relatively lower when compared to their share of total students (5%).

Figure 3. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Comparing Universities, Technological Universities and Institutes of Technology in terms of their composition of resources (Figure 4), the most striking result relates to the core budget of these organisation types: The core budget accounts only for 18% of total university sector resources, while the share of the core budget is 51% for the Technological Universities and 46% for the Institutes of Technologies. In contrast, the total University budget heavily relies on student fees, amounting to 47%, while Technological Universities and Institutes of Technology only draw about one third of their budget from student fees (34% and 36%, respectively).

Figure 4. Composition of resources. Universities and Institutes of Technology, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a steadily growing path of total enrolment, resulting in a 32% increase in the decade between 2011 and 2020 (Figure 5). Hereby, the increase is by and large equally distributed across the three main categories of the Irish HE system, superimposed only by the appearance of the Technological Universities. The latter represent mergers of five Institutes of Technology, which became two Technological Universities (TU Dublin and MTU) in the last two years, reflecting an internal shift of student shares between these HEI types.

Figure 5. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Figure 6 exhibits the development of academic personnel from 2011 to 2019, since data for 2020 is not yet available. The growth in total academic personnel (FTE) in Irish HEIs was 20% in this period, thus unable to keep full pace with the 25% increase in the total number of students (see Figure 5). This result is mainly due to the comparatively slower growth of academic personnel in the non-university sectors (Institutes of Technology and Technological Universities combined).

Figure 6: Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2019

Note: Data on academic personnel is missing for 2020.

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